

plant was 154.4% for Jhona 3491/IR6. This was based on simultaneous heterosis in plant height, number of productive tillers per plant, panicle

length, total florets per panicle, and 1,000-grain weight. Heterosis for yield for the best 4 crosses varied greatly from 13.9 to 154.4%.

Results indicate the potential for harnessing hybrid vigor in the development of relatively salt-tolerant strains of rice. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

CN704-7-3, a new variety for rainfed deepwater areas in eastern India

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Based on national performance in 1984-86, the 1986 annual rice workshop at Hyderabad recommended CN704-7-3

(IET9060) from the cross Pankaj/CN540 developed at RRS, for areas where water stagnates up to 100 cm during wet season (kharif) in West Bengal and Bihar. In six state adaptive trials in 1982-85, CN704-7-3 outyielded the checks Tilokkachari and Mahsuri by 25% (see table). CN704-7-3 yielded better than check 1 at several water depths (see figure).

CN704-7-3 is photoperiod sensitive

Performance of CN704-7-3 in state and national trials. India, 1982-86.

Trial and year	Site	Max water depth ^a (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
			CN704-7-3	Local check		
State adaptive 1982	Chinsurah	70	3.2	2.4	Tilokkachari	
	Nimpith	60	3.6	2.8	Mahsuri	
	1983	Hooghly	75	3.8	2.9	Mahsuri
		Chinsurah	75	3.9	2.9	Tilokkachari
	1984	Narendrapur	55	3.4	2.6	Mahsuri
1985	Burdwan	75	3.7	2.6	Mahsuri	
National PVT-5 1984	Cuttack	na	2.5	1.0	CR210-1018	
	Bhubaneswar	25	2.0	1.4	OR1 104	
	Patna	65	2.1	1.7	Janki	
	Sabour	na	3.2	3.0	Janki	
UVT-5 1985	Cuttack	na	3.3	3.1	CR1030	
	Bhubaneswar	na	1.8	2.0	Khajuriachaur	
	Chinsurah	65	3.0	2.0	Tilokkachari	
	Karimgunj	na	3.2	2.5	na	
	Malda	70	3.6	3.0	CN540	
	Ghagraghat	60	2.9	2.0	Madhukar	
	Patna	na	2.7	1.8	na	
	Arundhutinagar	na	4.9	4.5	Pizam	
Physiology screening	Calcutta	60	4.7	4.6	Pankaj	
	Chinsurah	65	2.1	0.9	Mahsuri	
	Cuttack	55	2.7	2.2	CR1018	
	Patna	50	3.4	3.0	IET8879	
	Titabar	50	3.5	3.1	Manoharsali	
UVT-5 1986	Chinsurah	110	3.0	1.1	TCA212	
	Malda	62	3.6	3.2	CN540	
	Pusa	85	2.2	1.8	TCA214	
	Ranital	65	2.2	1.7	CR1030	
	Faizabad	80	1.3	2.0	Pankaj	
Physiology screening	Cuttack	50	4.3	3.4	CR1018	
	Patna	50	3.2	2.2	Janki	
Mean (30 sites)			3.1	2.4		

^a na = data not available.

Yield performance of CN704-7-3 in different water regimes. Chinsurah, India, 1982-86.

and flowers 26-30 Oct. Depending on water depth, it reaches 150-175 cm height with 10-12 tillers/hill. The variety has very good submergence tolerance, kneeing ability, and drought tolerance at early vegetative stage. The panicle is about 22 cm long with good exertion, each accommodating about 175 grains. Grain is medium and bold (length-5.6 mm, breadth-2.8 mm, L:B-2.0) and 1,000-grain weight is 25 g. It possesses yellow hull at maturity, red kernel, and strong seed dormancy. The variety is moderately resistant to bacterial blight and moderately susceptible to blast.

CN704-7-3 yielded 3.1 t/ha (2.4 t/ha for check) in 30 locations and has been recommended for minikit demonstration trials in farmers' fields. □

Improved basmati donors

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Traditional basmati rices have tall plants, droopy leaves, high lodging tendency, relatively low grain weight,